

Challenges To Family Institution in India

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Introduction:

At the outset let me move a word of caution— it is hazardous to offer a generalized view of the nature and problems of the Indian family system which have persisted over the years, as the subject is quite complicated for the reason that the Indian society is very vast and is characterized by bewildering complexity. According to the 2001 census, India consists of 192.7 million households spread over 0.59 million villages and about 5,000 towns. The Indian society exhibits considerable variations between regions, between rural and urban areas, between classes, and finally, between different religious, ethnic and caste groups. The Indian society is, in fact, a congeries of micro-regions and sub-cultures and differences between which are quite crucial from sociological angles. Furthermore, the differences are also discernible with respect to the level of female literacy, sex ratio, age at marriage of girls, incidence of dissolution of marriage, household size, female workforce participation rate, marital practices, gender relations and authority structure within the family. Diversities inherent in Indian society are also reflected in the plurality of family types.

The virtual disappearance of traditional joint family from the urban scene, increase in the life expectancy of women from 23 years in 1901-10 to 65 years (it is higher than that of men by three years) in 2009, rise in the proportion of female headed households, decrease in the

average age of household heads, increase in the incidence of separation and divorce, greater tension and conflicts between wife and husband, parents and sons and between brothers, increased freedom of marital choice, passing of child marriages, shrinking of kinship ties, continuous consultations between sons and parents on familial matters, greater involvement of females in decision making process, increase in the mean age at marriage of female from 13 years in 1901 to 18.3 years in 2001, rise in the level of female education, decline in total fertility rate from 4.9 in 1971 to 2.76 in 2009 are concrete and clinching evidence to suggest a whole range of changes in the family system— its structure, functions, core values and regulative norms (Singh, 2004: 129-166). In course of these changes many new problems have surfaced, while some of the old ones, such as dowry, divorce, lack of intergenerational solidarity, discord between siblings and gender violence have got further intensified.

The passing of joint family system:

Since time immemorial the joint family has been one of the salient features of the Indian society. But the twentieth century brought enormous changes in the family system. Changes in the traditional family system have been so enormous that it is steadily on the wane from the urban scene. In villages the size of joint family has been substantially reduced or is found in its

fragmented form. Some have split into several nuclear families, while others have taken the form of extended or stem families. Extended family is in fact a transitory phase between joint and nuclear family system. The available data suggest that the joint family is on its way out in rural areas too (Singh, 2004: 134-140).

The joint family or extended family in rural areas is surviving in its form as a kinship group. The adults have migrated to cities either to pursue higher education or to secure more lucrative jobs or to eke out their living outside their traditional callings, ensuing from the availability of better opportunities elsewhere as well as the rising pressure of population on the limited land base. Many of the urban households are really offshoots of rural extended or joint families. A joint family in the native village is the fountainhead of nuclear families in towns. These days in most cases two brothers tend to form two independent households even within the same city owing to the rising spirit of individualism, regardless of similarity in occupation, even when the ancestral property is not formally partitioned at their native place.

With further industrial development, rural to urban migration, nuclearization of families and rise of divorce rate and the proportion of single member household is likely to increase steadily on the line of industrial West.

The emergence of financially independent, career-oriented men and women, who are confident of taking their own decisions and crave to have a sense of individual achievement, has greatly contributed to the disintegration of joint family. Disintegration of joint family has led to closer bonds between spouses, but the reverse is also true in certain cases. For many, nuclear family is a safer matrimonial home to a woman. In bygone days people generally lived in joint families, yet familial discord never escalated into extreme

physical violence or death, as we so often come across such instances in our day-to-day life and also know through national dailies, both electronic and print media.

Changes in authority structure:

Once the authority within the family was primarily in the hands of family elders commonly known as Karta in Hindi. The general attitude of members of the family towards the traditional patriarch was mostly one of respect. Now the people of younger generation, particularly those with modern tertiary education, do not seem to show the same reverence which their fathers had for their parents or elders. Changes concerning erosion of authority of old guards, particularly in matters of mate selection, are on gradual decline in rural areas too. This is not unusual when sons and daughters tend to possess a higher level of education and a greater degree of exposure of the world outside the family than ever before. Now boys and girls, contrary to the old practice, are beginning to assert their wishes in mate selection.

Changes in marital practices:

Child marriages have been prevalent in many cultures throughout human history, but have gradually diminished since some countries started to urbanize and experience changes in the ways of life for the people of these countries. An increase in the advocacy of human rights, whether as women's rights or as children's rights, has caused the traditions of child marriage to decrease greatly as it was considered unfair and dangerous for the children. Today, child marriage is usually practised in countries where cultural practices and traditions of child marriage still have a strong influence.

Yet another important marital practice is consanguineous marriage which has been the notable feature of a large segment of the Indian society since long. Through the ages the system

of cross-cousin and cross-uncle niece marriages has been the most favoured kind of marriage in South India. The most desirable mate for a man has been his own sister's daughter or mother's brother's daughter (Driver and Driver 1988; Nair 1978: 121, 131). In the face of rising dowry practices across the country consanguineous marriages have appreciably declined in South India in recent years. However, such marriages have remained tabooed among the vast majority of Hindus of North India. The Hindu Marriage and Divorce Act 1955 prohibits marriage among close relatives— called *sapinda* marriage. The *sapinda* relationship extends as far as the third generation in the line of mother and the fifth in the line of father. In North India only Muslims, certain scheduled castes and scheduled tribes tend to practise consanguineous marriages. Singh (1997: 8-9) has reported that most of the tribal groups practise consanguinity of both types such as marriages with the father's sister's daughter, the mother's brother's daughter and the elder sister's daughter.

The Indian society has been a mostly endogamous. Marriage within the same subcaste has been followed very strictly. The scheduled tribes are also endogamous, but most of the tribal communities practise clan exogamy (Singh 1997: 8). Polygamy, more particularly polygyny, has been one of salient features of Indian family. It has been more popular among Muslims than Hindus. Here it is not suggested that the incidence of polygyny is more common than monogamy. The polygamous males often derived support from age-old scriptures and mythological stories. But mainly those who had no issue from the first wife practised such marriages. With the rise in the level of literacy the incidence of polygyny has receded even among the Muslims even though such marriages have got full cultural and legal sanction. While monogamy is the predominant form of marriage, there are a large number of

tribes practising sororal polygyny and non-sororal polygyny (Singh 1997: 8).

Dissolution of marriage:

The dissolution of marriage has been quite uncommon and rare in India for a long time. In case of any crisis or threat to stability of marriage, caste, community, kinsmen, tended to have played a dominant say. People had both respect for and fear of social values and public opinion. Authority of community, though implicit, has been supreme. The system of religious belief has provided enough sustenance to the institution of marriage and family. Individual choice has always been subservient to the communal sentiment or public opinion. Hindu marriage is taken as a life-long union for the couple, as it is a sacrament, rather than a contract between the couple to live in a social union so long as it is cordially feasible. Even in the event of frequent mental and physical torture, most Indian women persist in marriage, since remarriage of divorced or separated women is quite difficult. Morality relating to sex is so highly valued that every male wants to marry a virgin girl only. In the past Hindus demanded pre-nuptial chastity on the part of both, but now it is by and large limited to females. Virginitly is regarded as the girls' greatest virtue and a symbol of respectability. Under the circumstances remarriage of women is so difficult that annulment of marriage is a very hard choice or option.

Domestic tension and violence:

Violence within family settings is primarily a male activity. The prime targets are women and children. The women have been victims of humiliation and torture for as long as we have written records of the Indian society. Despite several legislative measures adopted in favour of women during the last 150 years,

continuing spread of modern education and women's gradual economic independence, countless women have continued to be victims of discrimination and violence in the country (Singh 2002: 168). Increasing family violence in modern times has compelled many social scientists to be apologists for the traditional joint family- as happy and harmonious, a high-voltage emotional setting, imbued with love, affection and tenderness. India's past has been so romanticized by certain scholars that they have regarded the joint family as the best form of family.

There are data showing that in India 40 percent of women have experienced violence by an intimate partner. These stark figures underline the fact that, although the home and community are places where women provide care for others, they are also places where millions of women experience coercion and abuse. A study of five districts of the State of Uttar Pradesh has revealed that 30 percent of currently married men acknowledge physically abusing their wives (UNC 1997). Similarly, the multi-sectoral survey done by the International Clinical Epidemiologists Network (INCLIN) has reported that two out of every five married women reported being hit, kicked, beaten or slapped by their husbands.

With the rise in the level of education and exposure to mass media, women tend to have greater awareness of the notion of gender equality, faith in the effectiveness of legal action to protect their rights, and confidence in such institutions as family courts and certain voluntary organizations working for women. Yet there is no sign of abatement in gender related violence. Cases of domestic violence, like wife-battering and forced incest with the women of the household, are so personal and delicate that they are seldom reported to the police or law courts. We are sure that the recent legislation of anti-domestic violence act of 2005 would certainly

take care of the problem of gender-based violence of the Indian woman to a very large extent.

Conclusion:

The rise in the number of single member household, break-down of traditional joint family system, increase in cases of divorce, individual male migration to cities for work, erosion of authority of patriarch, the attrition of traditional family values, increase in the number of working mothers in cities and single parents, rise in domestic violence and practices of dowry, neglect of children and elderly, and poor regard for family laws are enough indications of the danger that the family and ultimately society are progressively facing in India. To combat the continuing erosion of values and the institution of family, there is a need of a set of strong, consistent policies to strengthen the Indian family system. Otherwise, India would be left with no choice, but to face the same problems which are generally faced by many families of developed countries now. To be more specific, the family needs an increased support in the areas of child care, social services, income assistance and health services than ever before. It is, however, recognized that the formulation of a comprehensive single national policy given the large size and heterogeneity of society like that of India is quite a difficult and cumbersome task.

At the same time it is also recognized that the formulation of new norms for a desired type of family system based on modern values is perhaps fraught with serious problems of various kinds. The state may not have the required political will to do so for some political expediency or mileage. Since ours is a soft state, law does not always prove to be so effective and hence, it may be difficult to regulate the Indian family system through a formal public policy. Increasing state intervention in an informal organization like family may be unpalatable to

many and it could be counterproductive as well. It is, however, not argued that the development of a national family policy would be an exercise in futility. In fact, in view of problems of various kinds and possible challenges of future there is a need of Family Policy Council in each state of India to conduct policy analysis, promote intergenerational solidarity, facilitate strategic leadership involvement and influence public opinion. It should be an autonomous entity with no link with the state except for financial aid and it should have a uniform purpose: helping family in responsible parenthood, serving as a voice for the family and assisting advocates for family ideals who aim to recapture the moral and intellectual high ground in the public arena. It is recognized that under the prevailing circumstances the civil society can play a more crucial and effective role than the state. In any case, because of rising individualism, competitiveness and openness in society and ever-increasing aspirations for higher attainments in life coupled with greater autonomy of individuals in society, an ideal family life may be a distant dream.

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